

Examining the Role of Financing from International Agencies towards Economic Outputs: A Case of Emerging Economies

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ABSTRACT: This research study analyzes the impact of International financial Institutions (IFIs) financing for the economic outputs of emerging economies. These institutional financings are inevitable for the economic growth of emerging economies. This research study used to collect the dataset from the database of World Bank. The time frame of dataset between the time periods from 1993 to 2022. The sample size for the research study is based on emerging economies. This study applies cross-sectional panel data analysis considering the economic outputs. This study reports that in most of the instances, international financing are the significantly variable for promoting economic activities in emerging economies. This research study describe the contribution of several international financial agencies before they have been made on specified International Financial Institutions. Majority of study done with World Bank (WB) and International Monetary Fund (IMF).

Keywords: International Financial Institution, EAGLE Emerging Economies, Economic Outputs of developing countries.

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1. Introduction

The international financial institutions (IFIs) are highly recognized by numerous countries as they serve the purpose to stabilize the emerging economies through their

economic growth. The economic output is the total of goods and services produced in a country. This research study high light the importance of IFIs assistance towards emerging economies. It is an important tool used for macroeconomic analysis. The IFIs help emerging economies towards contribution in employment creation, improve technologies and provide health care facilities. IFIs play a significant effect over the past years, and especially in the eve of financial crises in emerging economies (Ahmed et al 2024; Aslam et al 2024; Ashraf and Shabbir 2019; Bhatti et al 2023; Shabbir et al 2020; Nawaz et al 2022; Sikandar et al 2023). IMF performs outstanding performance during the financial and economic crisis (Lamdany & Wagner, 2011; Shabbir 2016;). In general, IMF provides loan for the development of emerging economies (Wallace, 1990). Researchers have conducted their analysis on the effect of international funding (e.g. World Bank, International Monetary Funds [IMF]) on the economic outcomes of countries.

According to Babb (2009), the World Bank program reduces the poverty in emerging economies. The structuralism theory conclude that financial development directly effects on the economic growth and resources strength and it insure that there is a negative relationship between real interest and investment. It may cause of financial sector under developed or over developed (Colin 2000; Aslam et al 2022; Ehsan et al 2023; Liu et al 2023; Liang et al 2023; Mughal et al 2023; Rawoof et al 2023; Rehman et al 2023;). It has been observed that more important is doing business which get competitive advantage. The IFC ranks them in global forum's World Competitiveness survey. Every government want to show its improvement in their rankings Schwab (2012).

IFIs funding address the economic growth of Emerging Economies. The absence of IFIs funds toward developmental project restricts the growth of emerging economies. Generally speaking, IFIs offers financial support to the emerging economies, which help to improve their economic outputs. The purpose of this study is used to investigate the relationship between economic growth and international agencies. The objective of the study is to analyze the impact of financing from international donors on the economic outputs emerging economies. This study is significant in the sense that it enables to identify the impact of different IFIs toward the economic growth. The data for this study is gathered from the database World Bank between the periods from 1993 to 2022 using the sample size emerging economies.

2. Literature Review

The present of International financial intuitions also served as a stamp of approval that provide financial assistant in the form of financial aid for developing countries. Such a bilateral assistant from the donor government Stubbs, Kentikelenis & King., (2016). IMF introduce the best source which able emerging economies to obtain more finance for economic development. Many years ago, the famous economist Goldsmith (1969) and Mckinnon., (1973) started payful attention to the benefits of financial structure development and financial independence, it increased economic output in emerging economies. In early 1990s, Mc kinnon (1991) could wrote it with confidence. The World Bank introduce my programs which reduce poverty in emerging economies Babb (2009).

Globalization Theory stated that Developing Countries organization take FDI in many ways. In first it's through gathering of Institutional factors and organization, different strategic activities take place to response the characteristics of developing countries, this study shows the logical extension of Globalization theory in a detailed content suggested by (Qing et al 2024; Tabasam et al 2024; Ur Rehman et al 2023; Wang et al 2023; Shabbir et al 2020; Nawaz et al 2022; Sikandar et al 2023). Convergence theory stated the research study narrates to numerous important strands of theory concerning with economic growth and financial-market development. There is first the literature on poverty traps and interpersonal convergence or divergence in economies with credit market imperfections, in particular Banerjee & Newman., (1993), Galor & Zeira., (1993), Aghion & Bolton (1997), and Piketty., (1997).

In the research done earlier most of studies checked the impact of World Bank and International Monetary Fund on economic output of emerging economies. Like, The World Bank's program reduce poverty in emerging economies Babb., (2009). IMF perform outstanding performance during financial and economic crisis by Lamdany & Wagner., (2011). IMF provided loan for the development of emerging economies Wallace., (1990).

H1: There is a significant impact of financing from World Bank on the economic output of emerging economies H2: There is a significant impact of financing from International Monetary Fund on the economic output of emerging economies H3: There is a significant impact of financing from International Bank of Reconstruction and Development on the economic outputs of emerging economies. H4: There is a significant impact of financing from International Development Association on the economic outputs of emerging economies. H5: There is a significant impact of financing from European Bank of Reconstruction and Development on the economic outputs of emerging economies.

3. Research Methodology

The impact of financing from IFIs behave differently on the economic outputs of diverse emerging economies. These emerging countries include (China, India, Russian Federation, Romania, and Turkey) over the period of 30 years from 1993 to 2022. We used panel data analysis in the research study. Though this cross-sectional panel data analysis we can measure the overall results of economic outputs and IFIs in emerging economies. This empirical study such as those done by Atje & Jovanovic (1993), Demirgüç-Kunt and Levine (1996), Xue et al 2024; Yan et al 2024; Shabbir 2021; Levine and Zervos (1998) and Arestis et al. (2001) are based on the cross-sectional panel data analysis country growth regressions analysis (OLS). In this research model there are five independent variables and eight dependent variables. This model enlightened the worth of International Financial Institutions financing on the economic outputs of emerging economies. Through this model we will see the impact of international financial institutions. We will see whether IFIs impact if significant or insignificant. First, we pick World Bank as an independent variable and one by one check its financing impact on each economic output, employment, FDI, GDP, GNI, Interest Expenditure, export and trade. Through econometric modelling, the result shows impact of international financial institutions. Then repeat the whole process one by one with

each international financial institution. After checking the result, we will comparison which institutional financing is highly significant for the economic output of emerging economies.

$$Y_{i,t} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 X_{i,t-1} + \alpha_2 X_{i,t-1} + \alpha_3 X_{i,t-1} + \alpha_4 X_{i,t-1} + \alpha_5 X_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

In this equation Y denoted to the outputs of emerging economies. Outputs like GDP, Employment etc I,t show the time period, whereas, α is constant value, $\alpha_1 X_{i,t-1}$ in this information x is showing the financing of World Bank as I mentioned one by one below equations. i,t-1 Show the time period t-1 is showing lag its mean if WB financing to country in 1993 it effect will be showing in 1994 due to lag value. Thus, $\alpha_2 X_{i,t-1}$ showing the impact of IMF financing, $\alpha_3 X_{i,t-1}$ showing the impact of International Bank for Reconstruction and Development financing, $\alpha_4 X_{i,t-1}$ for International Development Association and $\alpha_5 X_{i,t-1}$ for European Bank for Reconstruction and Development.

Empirical Analysis

This section presents the empirical findings of the study. To distinguish between fixed and random effect, first we apply Hausman test. The results are presented below:

$$EMPLOYENT_{i,t} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 FFWB_{i,t-1} + \alpha_2 FFIMF_{i,t-1} + \alpha_3 FFIBRD_{i,t-1} + \alpha_4 FFIDA_{i,t-1} + \alpha_5 FFEBRD_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon$$

Table 3 Hausman Test

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	41.8547	5	0.0000
Redundant Fixed Effects Tests			
Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	166.0144	(7,203)	0.0000
Cross-section Chi-square	411.6480	7	0.0000

In this above table 3 we can see the problem value of Hausman test is < 0.05 . The probability of Hausman test shows rejection of H_0 and accept H_1 . Its mean that the fixed effect model is appropriate to check the significance of IFIs financing on employment. The Redundant Fixed Effects / Likelihood test guide us to decide whether the variables are relevant or irrelevant in our research model. H_0 show the variables are not relevant and H_1 show the variables are relevant (Shabbir et al 2015). In this above table we can see the problem value of Likelihood test is < 0.05 . The probability of Likelihood test shows rejection of H_0 and accept H_1 . Its mean that all variable used in model are relevant.

Table 4 Fixed Effect Model

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
EBRD	-0.0005	0.0003	-1.5216	0.1297
IBRD	0.0002	0.0001	1.7517	0.0813
IDA	0.0001	0.0002	0.9529	0.3418
IMF	-0.0052	0.0018	-2.8861	0.0043
WB	0.0216	0.0043	5.0081	0.0000
C	4.0996	0.0831	49.3196	0.0000
Effects Specification				
Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)				
R-squared	0.8768			
	120.4006			
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000			

The fixed effect model gives preferences over the random effect model as the Hausman Test shows the P-value is 0.0000. In this situation, we reject H0 and accept H1 where there is one dependent variable employment and five independent variables. Among these independent variables the financing effect of International Bank for Reconstruction and Development, International Monetary Fund and World Bank's is significant on the economic outputs of emerging economies. Rest of two international financial institutions, International Development Association and European Bank for Reconstruction and Development's financing is insignificant on the economic outputs of emerging economies. We can say that there is significant impact of IBRD, IMF and WB's financing on the economic output of emerging economies (Shabbir 2018; Zhang et al 2023). Secondly if 1% increase in WB's financing cause 2% increase in employment. Among these IBRD, WB and IMF the World Bank results are must better than IMF and IDA. If we compare the results of IMF and IDA. The IMF's result is much better, because its problem value is 0.0043. The Fixed effect model shows the overall results are significant for the economic output of emerging economies.

$$EXPORT_{i,t} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 FFWB_{i,t-1} + \alpha_2 FFIMF_{i,t-1} + \alpha_3 FFIBRD_{i,t-1} + \alpha_4 FFIDA_{i,t-1} + \alpha_5 FFEBRD_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon$$

Table 5 Hausman Test

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	3.2707	5	0.6583

The random effect is appropriate for the dependent variable (Export) where IFIs emerging economies to enhance their exports in developed countries. It is the resource of revenue generation.

Table 6 Random Effect Model

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
EBRD	0.0030	0.0026	1.1627	0.2463
IBRD	0.0001	0.0008	0.1867	0.8520
IDA	-0.0060	0.0015	-3.9245	0.0001
IMF	-0.0067	0.0136	-0.4973	0.6194
WB	-0.1894	0.0311	-6.0710	0.0000
C	6.0234	0.6226	9.6741	0.0000
Effects Specification			S.D.	Rho
Cross-section random			0.4245	0.7675
Idiosyncratic random			0.2337	0.2325
Weighted Statistics				
R-squared	0.2189			
F-statistic	11.7703			
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000			

In above table 6 the P value of International Development Association is 0.0001 but the P value of World Bank is 0.0000 which is highly significant for the economic outputs of emerging economies. Rest of three international financial institutions International Bank for Reconstruction and Development, European Bank for Reconstruction and Development and International Monetary Fund shows the financing impact is insignificant on the economic output of emerging economies. Secondly if 1% increase in financing of WB cause 18.94% decline in export. R-squared 0.218901 which shows in panel data analysis our model contribution is 21.89%.

$$\text{Foreign Direct Investment}_{i,t} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \text{FFWB}_{i,t-1} + \alpha_2 \text{FFIMF}_{i,t-1} + \alpha_3 \text{FFIBRD}_{i,t-1} + \alpha_4 \text{FFIDA}_{i,t-1} + \alpha_5 \text{FFEBRD}_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon$$

Table 7 Hausman Test

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	128.2313	5	0.0000

Redundant Fixed Effects Tests

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	22.8404	(7,203)	0.0000
Cross-section Chi-square	125.4688	7	0.0000

The IFIs influence the FDI of emerging economies. In few emerging economies increase in FDI means to finance other developing countries if they get sufficient financing from IFIs (Shabbir 2016). The probability of Hausman test shows rejection of H0 and accept H1. Therefore, fixed effect is appropriate to check the significance of IFIs for economic outputs.

Table 8 Fixed Effect Model

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
EBRD	0.0260	0.0135	1.9301	0.0550
IBRD	-0.0047	0.0044	-1.0689	0.2864
IDA	-0.0071	0.0078	-0.9115	0.3631
IMF	0.0039	0.0690	0.0569	0.9546
WB	-0.8626	0.1631	-5.2882	0.0000
C	11.4310	3.1298	3.6522	0.0003

Effects Specification

Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)

R-squared	0.5557
F-statistic	21.1653
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000

International financial institution helps emerging economies to enhance their FDI. Through the financing of international financial institutions emerging economies increase their FDI. It is incepted step of FDI in other developing countries. Among these independent variables the effect of financing from European Bank for Reconstruction and Development and World Bank is significant on the economic outputs of emerging economies (Shabbir 2016). The WB financing result are much better. Because EBRD helps developing countries to improve their private sector and new venture, though they can be financing other developing countries.

$$\text{Gross Domestic Product}_{i,t} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \text{FFWB}_{i,t-1} + \alpha_2 \text{FFIMF}_{i,t-1} + \alpha_3 \text{FFIBRD}_{i,t-1} + \alpha_4 \text{FFIDA}_{i,t-1} + \alpha_5 \text{FFEBRD}_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon$$

Table 9 Hausman Test

Test Summary	Chi-Sq.		
	Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	16.2651	5	0.0061

Redundant Fixed Effects Tests

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	6.2972	(7,203)	0.0000
Cross-section Chi-square	42.4462	7	0.0000

The probability of Hausman test shows rejection of Null Hypothesis H0 and accept Alternative Hypothesis H1 Therefore fixed effect model is appropriate for analysis.

Table 10**Fixed Effect Model**

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
EBRD	0.0206	0.0130	1.5797	0.1157
IBRD	-0.0075	0.0042	-1.7675	0.0786
IDA	-0.0017	0.0076	-0.2304	0.8179
IMF	-0.0075	0.0668	-0.1133	0.9099
WB	0.1097	0.1577	0.6954	0.4876
C	-1.0291	3.0276	-0.3399	0.7343

Effects Specification

Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)	
R-squared	0.2989
F-statistic	7.2140
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000

In above table the effect of International Bank for Reconstruction and Development is significant on the economic outputs of emerging economies. Because its P value is 0.07. Gross Domestic Product is another dependent variable. It shows the overall productivity of country. It includes income of whole population as well as monetary element include in GDP. International financial institution helps the emerging economies to enhance their GDP. Through the financing of international financial institutions, the emerging economies increase their GDP. Secondly if 1% increase in financing of EBRD cause 2% increase in GDP. But if 1% increase in IDA financing result decreasing in GDP Because IDA major contribution for construction project while GDP related with the good and services of emerging economies (Shabbir and Wisdom 2020). R-squared 0.298956 which in panel data analysis our model contribution is 29.89%. IBRD stand for International Bank for Reconstruction and Development. This Bank financing for construction related project as we can all the construction projects bring a lot of employment opportunity in the country for example Metro Bas in Pakistan facilitate a lot of citizen as well as bring employment opportunities. Indonesian emerging economies start a lot of construction project in its cities Denpasar, Surabaya and Bali in their country with the help of IBRD.

$$\text{Gross National Income}_{i,t} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \text{FFWB}_{i,t-1} + \alpha_2 \text{FFIMF}_{i,t-1} + \alpha_3 \text{FFIBRD}_{i,t-1} + \alpha_4 \text{FFIDA}_{i,t-1} + \alpha_5 \text{FFEBRD}_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon$$

Table 11 Hausman Test

	Chi-Sq.		
Test Summary	Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	2.1810	5	0.8236

The probability of Hausman test shows rejection of H1 and accept H0. Its mean that the random effect model is appropriate for data analysis. Table 11 shows p-value is 0.8236. Therefore, we go for random effect model.

Table 12 Random Effect Model

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
EBRD	0.0254	0.0126	2.0108	0.0456
IBRD	-0.0093	0.0041	-2.2385	0.0262
IDA	0.0012	0.0072	0.1792	0.8579
IMF	0.0084	0.0648	0.1309	0.8959
WB	0.1837	0.1271	1.4449	0.1499
C	-2.4911	2.6044	-0.9564	0.3399

Effects Specification			
		S.D.	Rho
Cross-section random		0.7336	0.3017
Idiosyncratic random		1.1159	0.6983

Weighted Statistics	
R-squared	0.0490
F-statistic	2.1671
Prob(F-statistic)	0.058991

Table 12 shows how GNI effected by the financing of International financial institutions. IFIs helps emerging economies to enhance their GNI. Through the financing of International financial institutions emerging economies increase gross national income in their countries (Shabbir et al 2023). Among these independent variables the effect of Financing from International Bank for Reconstruction and Development and European Bank for Reconstruction and Development is significant on the economic outputs of emerging economies.

$$INTEREST\ EXPENDITURE_{i,t} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 FFWB_{i,t-1} + \alpha_2 FFIMF_{i,t-1} + \alpha_3 FFIBRD_{i,t-1} + \alpha_4 FFIDA_{i,t-1} + \alpha_5 FFEBRD_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon$$

Table 13**Hausman Test**

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	61.4216	5	0.0000
	Redundant	Fixed	
Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	10.5199	(7,203)	0.0000
Cross-section Chi-square	66.8543	7	0.0000

The results of table 13 show that fixed effect is appropriate

Table 14**Fixed Effect Model**

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
EBRD	0.0010	0.0046	0.2321	0.8166
IBRD	0.0028	0.0015	1.8610	0.0642
IDA	0.0100	0.0027	3.6506	0.0003
IMF	-0.1010	0.0240	-4.2037	0.0000
WB	0.2506	0.0567	4.4162	0.0000
C	-0.2743	1.0889	-0.2519	0.8014

Effects Specification

Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)

R-squared	0.377132
F-statistic	10.24263
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000

Interest Expenditure is another dependent variable. International financial institution helps the emerging economies to enhance their IE. International Financial Institutions helps emerging economies to face short term financial problems. IFIs help them to pay short term debt. Through the financing of international financial institutions emerging economies can pay their Interest to the borrowing countries (Fahamsyah et al 2023; Hayat et al 2022). Among these independent variables the financing effect of International Bank for Reconstruction and Development, World Bank, International Monetary Fund, International

Development Association is significant on the economic outputs of emerging economies. Emerging economies required financing for innovation and creativity. These International Financial Institutions provide them short term debt with with less interest rates. Therefore, these emerging economies escape them from high debt which affect their economic growth and financial stability.

$$TRADE\ VOLUME_{i,t} =$$

$$\alpha_0 + \alpha_1 FFWB_{i,t-1} + \alpha_2 FFIMF_{i,t-1} + \alpha_3 FFIBRD_{i,t-1} + \alpha_4 FFIDA_{i,t-1} + \alpha_5 FFEBRD_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon$$

Table 15**Hausman Test**

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	2.4657	5	0.7816

The probability of Hausman test shows the rejection of H1 and acceptance of H0. It means we go for random effect model.

Table 16**Random Effect Model**

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
EBRD	0.0024	0.0024	1.0032	0.3169
IBRD	0.0007	0.0008	0.9645	0.3359
IDA	-0.0066	0.0014	-4.6075	0.0000
IMF	-0.0078	0.0126	-0.6182	0.5371
WB	-0.1689	0.0289	-5.8345	0.0000
C	6.4403	0.5793	11.1171	0.0000
Effects Specification				
			S.D.	Rho
Cross-section random			0.4169	0.7882
Idiosyncratic random			0.2161	0.2118
Weighted Statistics				
R-squared	0.2326			
F-statistic	12.7312			
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000			
Unweighted Statistics				
R-squared	0.0146	Mean dependent var	3.6896	
Sum squared resid	30.2945	Durbin-Watson stat	0.1918	

Trade is another dependent variable we used in this study. IFI helps emerging economies to enhance their trade. Through the financing of International financial institutions, the emerging economies increase their exports in developed countries. In above table 4.16 the effect of financing from International Bank for Reconstruction and Development and European Bank for Reconstruction and Development is significant on the economic outputs of emerging economies.

4. Conclusion

Emerging Economies need finance for economic growth and International Financial Institution help them for economic development. As explained in the literature review, some researchers disagree with the facts that the impact of IFIs is significant in case emerging economies. Somehow, we agree with his statement because in data analysis it has been found that the economic outputs of emerging economies show the results of international financing institution financing is insignificant. But the truth is that most of results show the impact of the World Bank financings is significant on the economic growth of emerging economies. Therefore, the role of international financial institutions is significant on the economic development of emerging economies. The best and foremost favorable financial institution is the World Bank. The World Bank's financing impact is significant on the economic outputs of emerging economies.

In order to improve the quality of this study, we should include other emerging economies e.g. Bangladesh Iran, Nigeria Egypt and Poland. Other than these financial institutions included in this study, we should check out the impact of other financial Institution like International Labor Organization.

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